

The Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury: an Interagency Community Platform for Pre-clinical Data Management and Sharing

Maryann E. Martone^{1,2}, J. Russell Huie^{2,3}, PJ Axtman³, Lex Maliga Davis³, Gene Gurkoff⁵, Abel Torres-Espin^{3,4}, Jeffrey S. Grethe¹, Adam R. Ferguson^{2,3} + PRECISE-TBI

¹Dept of Neurosciences, University of California, San Diego

²San Francisco Veterans Administration Hospital

³Department of Neurological Surgery, Brain and Spinal Injury Center (BASIC), Weill Institute for Neurosciences, University of California, San Francisco

⁴School of Public Health Sciences, Faculty of Health, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Canada

⁵University of California, Davis

Maryann E. Martone: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8406-3871>

J. Russell Huie: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5594-4277>

PJ Axtman <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5158-6570>

Abel Torres-Espin <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9787-8738>

Adam R. Ferguson: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7102-1608>

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to acknowledge Drs. Catherine Johnson, Anita Bandrowski and Neil Harris for helpful comments. This work was funded by an interagency award from the Department of Veterans Affairs, Department of Defense and the National Institutes of Health awards I50BX005878; I01RX002245, I01RX002787; U24NS122732;

UH3NS106899 R01NS122888; as well as infrastructure support from the the Wings for Life Foundation and Craig H. Neilsen Foundation.

Abstract

The Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury (ODC-TBI.org) was launched in 2018 to support data sharing in pre-clinical TBI. As data science and artificial intelligence continue to advance, open sharing of high quality, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data has assumed critical importance to propel discovery science and as a countermeasure to some of the rigor and reproducibility problems plaguing translational research across biomedicine. Researcher-led specialist repositories like ODC-TBI serve as important hubs through which biomedical communities come together to define data sharing requirements for their respective domains in support of new requirements by funders and journals for routine data sharing. ODC-TBI is now the recognized data repository for pre-clinical TBI research, listed on the National Library of Medicine recommended repository listing, and is supported by the National Institute on Neurological Disorders and Stroke. ODC-TBI forms one of the critical infrastructure components of the PRE Clinical Interagency reSearch resourcE-TBI (PRECISE-TBI) project, an interagency effort to promote and support data sharing, rigor and reproducibility in pre-clinical TBI research. Through PRECISE-TBI, the ODC-TBI has conducted broad outreach, starting in 2022, resulting in a significant increase in the number of users, datasets uploaded and public data releases. PRECISE-TBI has facilitated the establishment of an Editorial Board providing community oversight of ODC-TBI policies and recommendations, e.g., the use of standards like common data elements (CDEs). Here we describe the current state of the ODC-TBI, including its organization and governance. We perform a detailed overview of public datasets to provide insight into data sharing practices, including the use of CDEs and ancillary practices such as providing links to publications and citing data. We examine the impact of the ODC-TBI by providing statistics on downloads per datasets and reuse of ODC-TBI data in published studies. The results provide insight into the growth trajectory of ODC-TBI and data sharing behaviors in pre-clinical TBI, but also point to areas where increased outreach, communication and training are needed to firmly establish a culture of data sharing.

Introduction

The Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury (ODC-TBI.org) was launched in 2018 to support data sharing in pre-clinical TBI. The ODC-TBI and its sister site, the the Open Data Commons for Spinal Cord Injury ([ODC-SCI.org](https://odc-sci.org)), were predicated on the belief that open data is critical for translational research and for addressing some of the reproducibility and transparency problems plaguing neurotrauma and other areas of translational research. Specifically, there has been a poor track record of translating studies conducted by a single lab on a single model into clinically meaningful treatments (Floyd et al., submitted). Advances in data science and artificial intelligence (AI) over the past decade promise to revolutionize our ability to analyze complex syndromes like TBI but they are critically dependent on the availability of large amounts of high quality data (Elshawi et al., 2018; Hawkins et al., 2020). Ready access to pre-existing datasets in preclinical neurotrauma research, collected across different laboratory settings, allow for powerful data analyses that are already leading to new treatments and insights into neurotrauma (Chou et al., 2022; Ferguson et al., 2014; Radabaugh et al., 2023; Torres-Espín et al., 2021). The rapid improvement in AI agents to assist researchers in coding and analysis also promise to open up public data archives to practicing bench scientists, allowing researchers to go beyond the group effects reported in research articles by providing access to analysis-ready subject-level data.

The opportunities afforded by access to primary research data have led to sweeping policies from funding agencies like the NIH to promote data sharing, dislodge questionable research practices and push researchers towards using public data. Funding agencies and journals are increasingly requiring open data sharing as a condition of funding and publication (M. Martone & Nakamura, 2022; *NOT-OD-21-013: Final NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing*, n.d.). More recently, the NIH indicated that pre-clinical labs needed to consider what have been termed “New approach methodologies” (NAMS) in addition to traditional animal research in all new grant applications (*NIH to Prioritize Human-Based Research Technologies*, n.d.). NAMS include “*ex vivo human-based approaches, including perfused human organs and precision-cut tissue slices; in vitro methods, including microphysiological systems and organoids; computational and artificial intelligence-based approaches; and combinations thereof*” (*NIH Funding Announcements to Align with NIH Initiative to Prioritize Human-Based Research*, n.d.). Preclinical research is therefore in the middle of a major transformation towards a more structured data-centric practice.

As data sharing starts to assume greater importance across biomedicine, publishing data has become a more formal process with data repositories like the ODC-TBI managing data submission, curation and publishing. Indeed, various organizations, including NIH, are starting to define desirable characteristics for scientific data repositories to ensure that data are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) (Wilkinson et al., 2016) (M. E. Martone, 2023). Such practices include the issuing of persistent identifiers like digital object identifiers (DOIs) for datasets, and implementation of community standards. ODC-TBI is now the NIH and NINDS recognized community hub for pre-clinical TBI research and is listed on the NLM-recommended repository listing. It provides the pre-clinical counterpart to the Federal Interagency Traumatic Brain Injury (FITBIR) database, which houses clinical TBI datasets.

ODC-TBI forms one of the critical infrastructure components of the PRE Clinical Interagency reSearch resourceE-TBI (PRECISE-TBI project), an interagency project involving the US Veterans Administration, NIH and the Department of Defense to promote data sharing, rigor and reproducibility in pre-clinical research. Cross-agency support for required data sharing recognizes TBI as a significant cause of disability and mortality in both military and civilian populations.

In this report, we provide an overview of the ODC-TBI, its organization and operations, and how it is operated as a community-governed hub for effective data sharing in preclinical TBI. We provide an in-depth analysis of the data published through the ODC-TBI as of July 2025 to examine current data sharing practices in these early days of data sharing, analyzing adherence to recommended standards such as metadata and CDEs and citing datasets in published studies. These analyses provide baseline data for measuring the impact of data sharing policies, willingness of researchers to comply with FAIR practices and highlight gaps in understanding or real world difficulties in implementing such practices that need to be addressed.

Methods

Architecture

The ODC-TBI portal (RRID:SCR_021736) is available at [ODC-TBI.org](https://odc-tbi.org). It was launched as a beta release in 2018, with the production release in 2022. The technical architecture is described in detail in (Chou et al., 2022). The ODC-TBI is built on the SciCrunch infrastructure, the same infrastructure as the ODC-SCI, launched in 2016. SciCrunch was developed and is maintained by the Neuroscience Information Framework (neuinfo.org; RRID:SCR_002894) and the NIDDK Information Network ([dkNET.org](https://dknet.org); RRID:SCR_001606) (Grethe, J. S., Bandrowski, A., Banks, D. E., Condit, C., Gupta, A., Larson, S. D., Li, Y., Ozyurt, I. B., Stagg, A. M., Whetzel, P.L., Marenco, L., Miller, P., Wang, R., Shepherd, G.M., Martone, M. E., 2014); (Surlles-Zeigler et al., 2021; Whetzel et al., 2015)). SciCrunch was built to allow communities to create customized data portals from a common software platform in order to decrease costs and promote cross-platform sharing.

Analysis

To provide insights into the state of data sharing practices within ODC-TBI, we performed an analysis of the datasets uploaded to the ODC-TBI as of July 2025, examining data sharing behavior within the ODC-TBI. We then performed a deeper analysis of the metadata of the 31 publicly available datasets as of that date. Depending on the type of analysis, we excluded some datasets so as not to skew the statistics. For each analysis, we identify the subset of datasets analyzed and the exclusion criteria. The different datasets analyzed are designated Dataset 1 (31 datasets), Dataset 2 (27 datasets) and Dataset 3 (30 datasets). A list of ODC-TBI datasets used for each is found in (M. Martone, 2025)

To analyze the content of ODC-TBI public datasets and the presence of key metadata, we mapped information provided in the descriptive metadata and data dictionary to a subset of study level Common Data Elements (CDEs) recommended by PRECISE-TBI (RRID:SCR_027597; PRECISE-TBI Data Dictionary Study Metadata CDEs V001.2) available from the PRECISE website (precist-tbi.org). Inclusion of these CDEs was examined by analyzing the data dictionaries that accompany each dataset for the presence of these variables and how they were structured. For this analysis, we used a beta version of the CDE mapping tool under construction by ODC-TBI to map public datasets to the nine core recommended variables, as specified in the ODC-TBI documentation ([Required variables | Open Data Commons](#)). Additionally we explored the use of a commercially available AI assistant for mapping data set variables against the CDEs. We uploaded the definitions of the PRECISE Core CDE's and the data dictionaries for each dataset to Claude AI (RRID:SCR_027603) Sonnet 4.0 (paid PRO version) with the prompt “Can you create a mapping between the variables in odctbi_####_dictionary and the PRECISE-TBI data dictionary?”.

Reuse of data was measured by citations and mentions in the published literature. To find citations to ODC-TBI data, we searched for each dataset DOI in the DataCite Commons (RRID:SCR_027609; <https://commons.datacite.org/>), Google Scholar (RRID:SCR_008878; <https://googlescholar.org>) and Google Dataset Search (RRID:SCR_027616; <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>). DataCite is the organization that mints DOIs for datasets. Google Dataset search is a dataset search engine which automatically indexes datasets marked up according to schema.org (RRID:SCR_018291), which has been implemented on the ODC-TBI website. DOIs were searched in the form:10.34945/#####, without the doi prefix. We also searched for the string “odc-tbi.org/data/” to identify articles that may have cited data via the URL. To look for mentions of the ODC-TBI based on its RRID (Bandrowski et al., 2015), we used the [dkNET.org](https://dknet.org) tool catalog (RRID:SCR_019227). RRIIDs are unique identifiers used to cite research resources used in a study, including software tools and data repositories. dkNET searches the full text of publications available in the open access subset of Pub Med Central. These citations included those that did not mention the dataset DOI but identified the dataset by URL or dataset number. Not included are any generic mentions about availability in the ODC-TBI where the specific dataset was not identified. For the purposes of this analysis, citations in preprints were counted. For each dataset mentioned, we characterized the citation type to distinguish between citations in originating publications that describe deposition of a dataset in the ODC vs. re-use of the data for another study. Reuse data was further divided based on whether the publication came from the original submitting lab or an external laboratory.

Data Availability

Datasets underlying the analyses presented in this study are available through Zenodo (RRID:SCR_004129), (M. Martone, 2025), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17945371>.

Results

Design of the ODC-TBI

Figure 1: Schematic layout of data sharing spaces in the ODC-TBI showing the progressive levels of data sharing from individual to public. Arrows indicate connections between spaces. Datasets entering the ODC-TBI (lower left) are initially private to the submitter. Labs are established by verified principal investigators who control membership within that lab. While an individual may then share data with others in the lab (individual → lab), only the PI may release data to those outside the lab. Sharing with the Commons provides limited access to other members of the ODC-TBI (Lab → Commons) while sharing to the Public allows access to the broader community (lower right). The Common space is currently being removed and so it is shown with a dotted line. Data may be shared with the public either via the Commons or directly from an individual lab.

The current organization of the ODC-TBI is shown in Fig. 1. The ODC-TBI is built around a series of data spaces with different degrees of access to data, from private to public. The basic unit of data sharing is the laboratory, which must be set up at the request of a principal investigator (PI) who is verified by the ODC-TBI leadership team. Once approved, the PI may then approve other members to join the lab space. The lab is therefore the conduit through which all data enters the ODC-TBI. Members of a lab upload data to a space private to the individual which can then be shared with the lab. Once in the lab space, however, only the PI may approve further sharing.

From the laboratory space, the PI can choose to share on a limited basis with other members of the ODC-TBI by releasing data to the ODC-TBI Commons, described in detail in Chou et al., 2022. However, we have found that most researchers share directly from the lab to the public space, so the Commons is currently being deprecated.

A PI may also publish their data to the public space by requesting a DOI. Note that data can be published directly from either the Lab Space or Commons Space (Fig. 1). All ODC-TBI datasets are released to the public under a CC-BY license, granting the right to reuse the data as long as attribution of the source is provided. To help with proper attribution, ODC-TBI provides a full data citation that can be included in the reference list according to recommendations for data citation (Fenner et al., 2019; Starr et al., 2015).

The private/public sharing features of ODC-TBI support consortia such as Translational Outcomes Project in NeuroTrauma (TOP NT; (Radabaugh et al., 2025; Wanner et al., 2025) and the Moody Project (Huie et al., 2022). Consortia use the platform to facilitate collaboration across sites and establish data collection and sharing strategies ahead of publication. TOP-NT is tasked with developing and validating a multidisciplinary battery of outcome measures or functional markers that distinguishes between types of injury induced pathology in TBI. The Moody Project brought together disparate outcomes from a fluid percussion injury model of TBI, including genomics, proteomics, and behavioral data. Because the data is managed via the ODC-TBI, as these consortia complete their studies, the data is easily released to the public (e.g., Andersen, et al., 2020; (Kislik et al., 2025).

ODC-TBI Governance

Data governance

The ODC-TBI accepts data primarily related to preclinical TBI studies. ODC-TBI therefore complements FITBIR which provides the data sharing platform for sensitive human data. No sensitive human data is allowed to be stored in either the public or private spaces of ODC-TBI, although we recently started to accept de-identified human data that is in compliance with regulatory requirements. ODC-TBI accepts subject level data in tabular form in comma separate values (CSV) file format. Upload of data to the private spaces has minimum requirements beyond inclusion of a subject ID column and valid column headers, e.g., no spaces. We encourage submitters to use a data quality checking tool (Fond et al., submitted) and programmatic API made available through the ODC Sandbox (<https://fdilab.gitbook.io/open-data-commons/odc-tool-sandbox/tool-sandbox>) to help identify data quality issues such as missing values or problems with CSV formatting. This tool is described in more detail in Fond et al. (submitted). Users may also upload additional files containing details about methodology and a data dictionary, but neither are required for data in private spaces.

To ensure that public data is FAIR, ODC-TBI implements additional requirements in order to receive a DOI such as organizing the data according to tidy format, an analysis ready format that maximizes flexibility in reuse (Wickham, 2014) Each public data set must also be accompanied by a detailed data dictionary. Submitters are encouraged to provide links to related publications and additional materials like protocols, related datasets, etc. More detail about standards supported by ODC-TBI can be found in Fond et al., (submitted).

ODC-TBI Editorial Board:

The ODC-TBI has recently established an Editorial Board (EB) comprising an Editor In Chief and members of the pre-clinical TBI community. The EB therefore provides a layer of community governance ensuring that ODC-TBI serves and is responsive to its target community (Lin et al., 2020),(Bilder et al., 2015). The EB and curatorial staff (CS) oversee the publication of ODC-TBI datasets on the public portal and provide input into publishing policies implemented by the ODC-TBI. Datasets submitted for publication undergo a curatorial review for compliance with ODC-TBI standards and data quality checks (Fond et al., submitted). Data quality checks are performed by a combination of automated and human review to identify issues such as adherence to tidy format, availability of key metadata and inconsistencies between the data dictionary and the dataset values. The ODC-TBI does not perform or confirm any scientific analyses on submitted data. The metadata provided for each dataset is reviewed by two EB members and CS to ensure that the dataset is appropriate for ODC-TBI, is adequately described and the necessary study level metadata, e.g., species, TBI model, is provided. The editorial process was patterned after that developed by the ODC-SCI (Torres-Espin et al., 2022), although standards and recommendations are set separately for each community. If a submitter wants to release more than just tabular data supported by the ODC, we work to identify an appropriate repository specialized for other data types and provide a link to the dataset as part of the metadata. For example, the dataset published by (Koloski & Ramanathan, 2025) provides a link to the primary physiological data hosted in the DANDI archive (RRID:SCR_017571).

The EB is also responsible for recommending data standards in the ODC. For example, they recently voted to recommend a set of 9 PRECISE Study Level CDEs (RRID:SCR_027597; LaPlaca et al., this issue) to be included in each dataset that covers core attributes of a TBI study (Table 2). Given the variety of data that comes into the ODC-TBI, the EB voted to forgo strict requirements. Instead, submitters are provided instructions on the recommended CDEs and given feedback on missing data elements by reviewers.

Data sharing via the ODC-TBI: Patterns and trends

Growth of the ODC-TBI

Data sharing via ODC-TBI initially was anemic, with a very small number of data uploads and public sharing for the first three years (Fig 2) when ODC-TBI was available on-line in beta release. As shown in Fig 2, the number of labs, users and datasets shared all increased substantially starting in 2022. This increase could be directly tied to outreach events conducted at the National Neurotrauma Society (NNS), Military Health System Research Symposium meeting and the Society for Neuroscience (SFN) annual meetings in conjunction with PRECISE-TBI starting in 2022. At this time, the production version of ODC-TBI was officially launched. To support the community in developing the required data management and sharing plan (DMSP) for new NIH grant applications, the ODC-TBI provided a template with sample DMSP text available from a link from our home page, highlighting standards and metadata requirements needed for utilizing the ODC-TBI as the designated data sharing repository for

NIH funding applications. To date, the plan has been accessed or downloaded more than 1000 times.

Figure 2: Analytics on population of the ODC-TBI through June 26, 2025

ODC-TBI provides a full suite of analytics on the website updated roughly quarterly. The following statistics were taken from the June 26, 2025 report (Fig. 2). Membership totaled 129 laboratories (Fig 2B) and 417 members that uploaded a total of 283 non-test datasets (Fig. 2A). Fifty five labs (43%) have uploaded at least one dataset, with the TOP-NT Consortium holding the largest number of datasets (87). Fig. 2C gives a breakdown of datasets at the different data sharing levels. At the time of analysis, 31 datasets were shared with the public (Dataset 1), with an additional 6 shared among ODC-TBI members in the common space. The bulk of data are in the lab spaces (183). Only 63 datasets are in the private upload space, however, indicating that the majority of datasets (78%) have been actively shared with others.

Overview of ODC-TBI public datasets

An overview of the content of public datasets available as of July 2025 is shown in Fig 3. For content analysis, we utilized 27/31 datasets (Dataset 2), excluding one dataset not directly TBI-related ([dataset 1187](#)), and 3 datasets that were related to other datasets and therefore shared all subject metadata. The 27 datasets analyzed were published by 15 different labs, four of which were led by PRECISE investigators. Combined, these datasets represent a total of 4,725 subjects, the vast majority of which are rodents (Fig 3A). Thirteen of the 31 datasets

include a detailed protocol, either directly uploaded or via a link to a protocol hosted by protocols.io (Zezong et al., submitted).

To categorize these datasets along key dimensions, metadata contained in the data descriptions and data dictionaries was structured according to a subset of the recommended PRECISE-TBI Study Level Metadata CDEs (Fig 3). Beyond the heavy bias towards rodents, a striking finding is the domination of male-only studies in the public space (66%), with mixed studies comprising only 28%. In fact, there is only a single female-only study in the public data. Looking at individual subject metadata, the bias is even greater than these statistics suggest as the dataset of Chou et al. (2022) representing an aggregated dataset of 11 preclinical studies comprising 1250 subjects, contains only 6.24% of female animals. In contrast to the heavy bias in sex and species, these datasets are derived from a variety of preclinical models (Fig 3B) and assessment types (Fig 3D), with 12 studies employing >1 assessment type. The average study duration across datasets was 56 days, ranging from 4 hrs to 1 year with a median value of 25 days. We plotted the time intervals studied across all datasets (Fig 4). There looked to be little coherence in the number or spacing of time points collected in longitudinal studies, although we did not perform a deeper analysis to compare time intervals with other study dimensions, e.g., injury severity, that might have correlated with intervals chosen. Chou et al. (2022) reported a similar finding for their set of 11 aggregated studies.

Figure 3: Overview of content of the ODC-TBI as of July 2025. Metadata was extracted from the titles and descriptions provided and aligned to the ODC-TBI recommended variables (Table 1). Results are shown for Species (A), TBI Model (B), Sex of animal (C) and assessments performed categorized by general type.

Figure 4. Mapping of time points sampled after TBI in 24 ODC-TBI public datasets.

Use of Common Data Elements in public ODC-TBI datasets

NIH has invested heavily in the creation and use of CDEs as their implementation can greatly improve interoperability and re-usability across datasets (Kush et al., 2020). TBI was one of the first pre-clinical domains to create a set of CDEs to aid in mapping rodent data with clinical data contained in FITBR (LaPlaca et al., 2021). As detailed in a companion paper in this issue, PRECISE-TBI has been working with the greater TBI community to further develop and refine the initial set of CDEs created in part by TOP-NT. The EB voted to monitor datasets for a minimal set of study and subject level variables and to recommend that the PRECISE-TBI CDEs be used for recording this information where appropriate (Table 1).

SubjectID: The subject ID used to uniquely identify a subject within a study

SpeciesTyp: Type of organism species for a particular subject

SpeciesStrainTyp: Type of the animal strain (for mice and rat) for each subject

***AgeVal:** Age of the animal at the time of procedure in weeks. If additional units are used, please include the appropriate Unit of Measurement companion CDE.

***BodyWgtMearVal:** Value of measurement of animal weight; use the appropriate companion Unit of Measurement CDE.

SexTyp: Type of organism sex as determined by observation

InjGroupAssignTyp: Type of group assignment for an individual subject

TBIModelTyp: Type of traumatic brain injury (TBI) model(s) used to induce the mechanism of TBI.

InjElapsedTime: The elapsed time from the time of injury. If additional units are used, please include the appropriate Unit of Measurement companion CDE.

Table 1: Core PRECISE CDEs recommended by ODC-TBI. These CDEs were extracted from PRECISE-TBI Data Dictionary General V001.2 with the exception of SpeciesTyp which was retained from PRECISE.CDE.V001.0_Metadata Core variables. Data dictionaries for PRECISE CDEs are included in the associated data (Martone, 2025)

To gain a better understanding of the presence of key metadata within data files, we analyzed the 26 of the 27 datasets in Dataset 2 for eight elements listed in Table 1. Dataset #954 was excluded because it contained deidentified human clinical data. Subject ID was dropped from the analysis because all datasets uploaded to ODC-TBI are required to have a column labeled Subject ID. We looked for the presence of these data elements in the data dictionary (Table 2), and whether it was structured according to the recommended CDE.

	AgeVal	BodyWgt MearVal	InjElapsed Time	InjGroup AssignTyp	Sex Typ	Species StrainTyp	Species Typ	TBIModel Typ	Average
Number (out of 26 total studies)	16	10	19	24	21	18	18	10	17
Unique Values	6	4	12	8	4	7	4	6	6.375
Exact match CDE Set	8	2	2	3	8	4	8	3	4.75
Percentage using a given	64	40	76	96	84	72	72	40	68

CDE:									
Average number of variables per dataset	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.44

Table 2: Mapping of 26 public datasets against PRECISE core variables recommended by ODC-TBI. The datasets listed in [data file 2](#) were used in the analysis but with the additional exclusion of dataset 954 which contained de-identified human data. When 2 or more datasets were directly related to each other, i.e., same subjects, we only mapped one of the dataset as the metadata was the same across them. Number = number of datasets containing the data element; Unique value = number of different labels used for the data element; Exact match CDE set = Is the label for the data element an exact match with a public released version of preclinical CDEs; Percentage using a CDE = percentage of datasets that utilize a given CDE; Average number of variables = average number of the 8 variables measured.

The majority of datasets submitted had most of the variables present (average 5.4 out of 8 total); many of the datasets that were missing a variable within the dataset had the information in the dataset description, as the variable applied at the study level, e.g., all subjects were Sprague-Dawley rats. There was quite a bit of variation in how they were named, with an average of 6 unique names per variable. Injury Elapsed Time (time after injury when first measurements were performed) exhibited the most variance (12 unique values), followed by Injury Group (8 unique values). Even relatively straightforward variables such as Sex had 4 different labels. For the most part, however, it was easy to perform the matching and both the human and the AI made the same judgments about the correct mapping when there was some ambiguity.

We then checked the variable labels of the mapped recommended data elements to PRECISE-TBI CDEs. As the CDE recommendations were only posted on the ODC-TBI starting in Feb 2025, we were not expecting much use of the PRECISE-TBI CDEs in earlier datasets. We were surprised, however, to find that quite a few datasets within the ODC-TBI showed evidence of conforming to some common standard for variable naming. We went back and examined the variable names against earlier versions of the preclinical TBI CDEs released in 2021 (LaPlaca et al., 2021) by PRECISE and found evidence that at least 3 versions of the CDEs had been used in ODC-TBI datasets. Even among this modest set of 8 high level core variables, CDE changes occurred over the multiple versions. Some were simple name changes where the name changed but not the definition or permissible values, e.g., AnimalSexVal → SexTyp. In other cases, the definition changed, e.g., age was defined as months in the Original FITBIR version, and then in weeks for subsequent PRECISE versions. New CDEs were added to the set, e.g., BodyWgtMeasrVal, while others were dropped, e.g., species was dropped in V001.2. These results highlight the importance of assigning version numbers and tracking changes at the individual CDEs.

Measuring the potential impact of ODC-TBI data

The ODC-TBI implements several methods to measure impact of the public datasets, in accordance with efforts such as “Making Data Count” (Kratz & Strasser, 2015), such as tracking views and downloads per dataset, and also provides a full data citation per dataset in accordance with Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles (Fenner et al., 2019).

Web traffic

Traffic to the ODC-TBI website grew dramatically between 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 5) with overall traffic (new + returning visitors) doubling. Returning visitors continued to grow through 2024 indicating that ODC-TBI was being established as a community site. Current trends as of June 2025 suggest that we will surpass our 2024 totals in both new and returning visitors, indicating a healthy growth in the user base. The ODC-TBI has a global reach, with the US followed by Canada and China providing the top sources of traffic. Within the US, access is broadly distributed geographically (Fig 5C).

Figure 5: Web site traffic as of June 26, 2025 showing: A) new (orange/top line) vs returning (green/bottom) visitors to the website; B) Geographical location by country of web site traffic with the color key shown on the right of the panel; C) Detailed view of location of views from the United States according to city. The larger and darker the circles, the higher the number of visitors.

Dataset downloads

Figure 6: Number of downloads per dataset as of August 2024 (blue) and July 2025 (red). Datasets, identified by their ODC-TBI accession number, are ordered roughly in chronological order of original publishing date, from earliest to most recent.

As of July 2025, ODC-TBI datasets have been downloaded over 750 times. Fig 6 shows the number of downloads per dataset. All datasets have been downloaded multiple times (red bars). Comparison of downloads between August 2024 (blue bars) and July 2025 (red bars) show that datasets continue to be downloaded regardless of publication date. To examine whether providing a direct link to the data in the ODC-TBI in the originating publication increased downloads, we looked at the originating publication, i.e., the publication where the data were first described and where deposition in the ODC-TBI was acknowledged, for how the data availability statement was structured. Of the 30 datasets analyzed, 19 provided a link to the originating publication. We were able to track down an additional 6 originating publications based on titles and authors for a total of 25 papers. We excluded 3 of these publications because they were published several years before the data were published. Of the 22 originating publications remaining, 14 included no reference to data being deposited within the ODC-TBI (63.3%), 7 included the DOI (31.8%) and 1 made a general reference to data being available in the ODC-TBI (4.5%). Overall, the average number of downloads for datasets not linked via the originating publication was higher (40) than those with a link (22), although these numbers do not take into account publication date. Nevertheless, these results suggest that an important number of downloads are potentially driven through direct access via the ODC-TBI rather than simply following links from a published manuscript.

Re-use of ODC-TBI data: citation analysis

To examine citation practices and reuse of ODC-TBI data, we tracked down citations of ODC-TBI data, using three different methods (Table 3).

Citation statistic	Total
Datacite citations	6
Google Scholar citations	17
Google Dataset Search citations	3
CitationType:Originating	14
CitationType:Reuse (Self)	2
CitationType:Reuse (External)	5

Table 3: Citation statistics for ODC-TBI datasets. The total number of DOI citations found in each of the 3 indices checked is given in the first 3 rows. The last 3 rows contain the number of citations that could be tracked down according to type. Originating: citation in the publication that first described the data; Reuse (Self): citation by the same research lab that deposited the data; Reuse (External): citation of the data by another research group.

Substantially different counts of DOI citations were obtained from the three different methods. Google Dataset Search was the lowest; it did not pick up many of the ones we identified manually. However, whether or not an ODC-TBI dataset is listed in Google Dataset Search appears somewhat arbitrary, as it is dependent on Google crawling our website. We found that many datasets were missing from the search index and therefore citation statistics were not available. Google Scholar allowed us to identify the most citations because we could search through the full texts of the biomedical literature. We found at least one dataset cited in an originating publication that was neither listed by DataCite or found via Google Scholar, and one which was cited in the reference list that was found by Google Scholar and not DataCite. Only one dataset citation was listed in DataCite and not Google Scholar. We could discern no pattern in which datasets were picked up by which methods, i.e., whether the DOI was in the data availability statement or the reference list.

The majority of citations (14/21, 66.6%) derived from originating publications, where the author referenced deposition of the data in the ODC-TBI. Seven citations were considered to be examples of re-use (33.3%), either by the original research group (2) or by others (5). For example, (Buccilli, 2025) utilized a de-identified human dataset (Nielson et al., 2023) to look at the impact of various injury parameters on the development of post traumatic stress disorder. (Agarwal & Zhang, 2025) included ODC-TBI data (Norris et al., 2024) in a training set for a new biofeedback tool for Neuro-AIDS. Thus, both download statistics and data citations show that data in the ODC-TBI is being accessed and used.

Discussion

While the ODC-TBI began operation in 2018, it was not officially launched as a production platform until Jan 2022. Since the production launch, the number of labs registered and datasets uploaded has increased steadily, due in large part to outreach events held at the scientific meetings in collaboration with PRECISE-TBI. These outreach events also coincided with the launch of the new NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy, likely increasing interest in these events in the research community. Despite positive growth in overall use of the platform by both individual labs and consortia like Top-NT, we would describe the number of public datasets as modest compared to the number of labs and users. In fact, the majority of labs that have registered in the ODC-TBI have yet to upload a dataset. Despite the relatively small numbers, we are definitely on an upward trajectory for submissions as the new NIH data policy continues to come into play and there is greater awareness of the importance of AI-ready public data in a field.

ODC-TBI as a specialist repository: standards and scope

Although we do not know the number of grants that have been submitted specifying the ODC-TBI as the designated repository, the sample DMS plan provided by the ODC-TBI has been viewed at least 1000 times. Nevertheless, researchers do have choices about where to store their data. The biomedical data repository ecosystem is complicated, with a patchwork of specialized repositories, generalist and institutional repositories providing services for biomedicine (Murphy et al., 2021). The ODC-TBI is considered a specialist or domain-specific repository in that it is specialized for data from pre-clinical TBI studies. Other specialist repositories are organized around data types, e.g., the Cell Image Library, or data types and/or domain, e.g, Cancer Imaging Archive, OpenNeuro, which house specific data types (images) within a domain (cancer and neuroscience). In contrast, the generalist repositories such as Dryad and Figshare will accept all domains and datatypes, and some, e.g., Vivli, will accept sensitive human subject data as well.

Specialist repositories like the ODC-TBI offer benefits over the generalist repositories including implementation of standards, curation and specialized tools for working with the data. For these reasons, the recognized best practice by NIH and others is to deposit data into a specialized data repository if one is available (*Selecting a Data Repository*, n.d.). Although specialist repositories have recognized benefits, they come with more requirements than generalist repositories. ODC-TBI, like most specialist repositories, e.g., SPARC, OpenNeuro and DANDI, require submitted data to adhere to specific standards as a condition of acceptance (Bandrowski et al., 2021; *DANDI Archive*, n.d.; Osanlouy et al., 2021; Poldrack et al., 2023; Subash et al., 2023a, 2023b). All have requirements for data format, data documentation and metadata that are enforced through automated tools and/or human curators. Population of these repositories therefore requires the support and cooperation of the community they serve, specifically the effort of investigators and their trainees to meet standards, or funder mandates to provide incentives for going through the extra effort. Specialist repositories are well aware that without this support and funder incentives, researchers can and will deposit their data in a generalist repository with fewer standards and little to no curation (Subash et al., 2023b).

However, in the absence of standards, while data might be findable and accessible, it will fall well short of the interoperability and reusability requirements of FAIR. Therefore, data repositories such as the ODC-TBI must build a community while engaging in a balancing act, ensuring high quality and standards-based data without imposing too high a burden on the data submitter.

In general, ODC-TBI tries to implement a balanced approach where the workload required to produce FAIR data is spread across the data submitter, the ODC and the data consumer, rather than exclusively on the data submitter. We believe standards and requirements should provide a tangible benefit for the data submitter, e.g., by improving findability, documentation and reusability within the lab. In this way, ODC requirements address some of the critical shortcomings of current lab data management practices, e.g., lack of metadata, proprietary or poorly formatted data, lack of documentation (Borghi & Van Gulick, 2018; Fouad et al., 2023). To help users with these requirements, we employ both curators and supporting tools. For example, ODC-TBI assists users in creating a data dictionary by creating a template with all variables in the data set listed. By putting their data into analysis ready form, and documenting their data with a data dictionary and critical metadata, investigators ensure that their own data can be reliably found, accessed, interpreted and reused by themselves, their lab and colleagues, now and in the future. Indeed, anecdotal testimonials from multiple repositories suggest that making data FAIR for themselves is one of most significant benefits for data submitters (M. Martone, 2023). Moreover, as described in Zezong et al. (this issue), while these efforts can initially be time consuming, as labs develop the experience and standard operating procedures around data, the process of successfully achieving the FAIR principles and meeting the standards of specialty repositories such as the ODC-TBI become significantly easier.

The ODC-TBI EB also provides for community oversight, in accordance with the TRUST (**T**ransparency, **R**esponsibility, **U**ser focus, **S**ustainability, **T**echnology) principles and principles of open infrastructure (Bilder et al., 2015; Lin et al., 2020). The EB is responsible for setting editorial policies such as required metadata and other standards. The first recommendation of 9 CDEs derived from the PRECISE-TBI general core set of CDEs was added to the instructions to ODC-TBI submitters in February 2025. The EB elected not to make these required as it recognized the variety of data types coming into the ODC-TBI. It also recognized that the CDEs and the tools for working with them are still a work in progress (LaPlaca and Harris, this issue) and so setting strict requirements at this time would likely be counterproductive. Although not required, we find that data submitters readily comply with instructions and requests to supply missing metadata. Our experience is similar to ODC-SCI, where the metadata per dataset improved and the use of CDEs increased significantly after instructions and feedback were provided (Soren et al., 2024). These results suggest that community repositories can still increase the quality of their data without imposing strict requirements if requests are reasonable. Indeed, we found evidence that researchers do use CDEs in the absence of ODC-TBI requirements, although the CDEs are somewhat unstable. As the CDEs become stabilized and researchers start to utilize them prospectively to collect data (Zezong et al., this issue), we expect that more automated harmonization across preclinical TBI datasets will be possible.

Use and interest in the ODC-TBI

Metrics indicate that ODC-TBI has a broad reach geographically, a growing user base and a healthy number of returning visitors. In addition, the number of downloads per dataset suggests that ODC-TBI data is being accessed. Citation analysis uncovered 7 articles that used an ODC-TBI dataset for reanalysis. Given the relatively small number of public datasets, the number is encouraging. Unfortunately, tracking down citations of ODC-TBI data, or indeed any datasets, is still very difficult. Journals and publishers declared their support for supporting data citations with the publication of the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles by FORCE11 and subsequent work to create the necessary implementations (Martone et al., 2014; Cousijn et al., 2018; Fenner et al., 2019). In accordance with recommendations on implementing data citation, ODC-TBI provides a DOI, full machine-readable citation metadata and provides a full data citation for each article (Fenner et al., 2019). However, our results and others (Lowenberg, 2021) show that data citation has not yet been embraced by either the publishers or, indeed, by researchers themselves. Unlike the standard method for referencing an article in a research paper, authors still use many ways to refer to a data set, making it difficult to search for these citations. We were surprised that many originating publications do not mention deposition of data at all, and most datasets do not provide a link to the originating publication, leading to a disconnect between these two research outputs.

Our results suggest that the concept of data citation is perhaps new to researchers and has not been internalized in a manner similar to citing narrative works. We have thus started to provide full citation information and instructions in the editorial review to data submitters. In fairness to researchers, the process of coordinating the publication of the article and the dataset to ensure that the appropriate identifiers are linked is currently not trivial. Researchers have to have their data uploaded and published in time to cite the DOI in the manuscript before publication. Once the manuscript is published and receives a DOI, the author has to go back to the ODC-TBI and link the paper, which currently requires administrative access. Given the data publication is not a priority of researchers, the process is often incomplete. However, even when data is cited properly, the pipelines for tracking these citations are not working very well resulting in few citations being present in DataCite (Lowenberg, 2021). These findings suggest two critical needs: more education to train researchers on the ins and outs of data publishing and citation, and better tracking tools for individual investigators, data repositories, universities and government sponsors to know that data is being successfully shared, reused and cited.

Ensuring that data are properly cited in research papers through their persistent identifiers is integral to the “Publication of the Future” (PoF) concept promoted by PRECISE-TBI (Zezong et al., submitted). To address transparency and reproducibility, PRECISE-TBI is encouraging researchers to think of a publication not as a single paper, but as a collection of linked study products, including data, protocols and code. Each of these are prepared and published as separate products of research on specialized platforms, freeing them from constraints imposed by the journal article. The PoF is thus a collection of research objects optimized for reuse, which can be easily found, used and cited independently. Critically, as each of the components

of this PoF receives a unique identifier accompanied by its own metadata, these products can be cited and linked across platforms (See Zezong et al., this issue, for some examples).

Where are we going?

The ODC-TBI was founded on the premise that open sharing of analysis-ready data would provide a substrate for both addressing some of the rigor and reproducibility problems inherent in much of translational research and accelerating the identification and testing of new treatments for neurotrauma (Chou et al., 2022; Radabaugh et al., 2023, 2025). As discussed in Ferguson et al. (submitted), access to large pools of data suitable for AI and machine learning approaches (AI/ML) are critical for addressing fundamental, persistent problems in preclinical TBI in measuring injury severity and matching pre-clinical to clinical injuries and outcomes. The rapid advance of AI/ML promises further discoveries, leading to the current push from funders for data that is AI/ML ready (Clark et al., 2024).

While we typically think of reuse in the context of new discoveries, providing ready access to a large pool of subject level data can also provide significant value to the field of TBI research. Several key examples include helping investigators in implementing new methods, identifying comparable data sets that would improve power analyses during experimental design, facilitate meta-analysis and meta-research (Iorio et al., 2024), and improving the rigor of their studies. Sharing data can facilitate collaborations and cooperation in the field, both helping investigators identify individuals with similar interests and outcome measures, but also creating a standard format and sharing platform for data, making the harmonization of findings more seamless. Even in these early days of data sharing, these metaanalyses are revealing perhaps where the field as a whole needs to go. For example, as recounted in LaPlaca et al. (submitted), analysis of the same outcome measures across different laboratories as part of TOP NT show that even when using the same behavioral tests, there is surprisingly little overlap in the measures reported. Being able to see what variables are collected and how they are structured can provide a means of defining critical standards for comparability across studies.

AI-driven advances will also require that more data be available and that biases, such as the still significant bias towards male animals, be addressed, which will require greater input from the preclinical TBI community. The good news is that AI also has significant promise to transform data operations across the entire data lifecycle, from lab management to data publishing. We are already using them in our curation workflow. The faster we adapt to new standards, and the more data we upload in the next few years, the faster the transition to the implementation of highly automated data management tools. AI agents can also assist in making public data more accessible and useful not only to data scientists conducting complex analyses, but for more tasks more immediately beneficial to the bench scientist. “Vibe coding” allows humans to direct an analysis through natural language prompts while the AI writes the actual code thereby lowering the barrier for domain experts to work more easily with public data (Chow & Ng, 2025; Moore & Tatonetti, 2025). Public repositories like ODC-TBI combined with AI therefore can play a vital role in fulfilling new mandates to tie animal research more closely to clinical data by allowing researchers to employ more data driven approaches to designing experiments and creating models. It is critical that over the next decade investigators start to leverage new tools

and resources to improve the rigor and reproducibility of the scientific endeavor. Optimizing data management, developing a publication of the future, and sharing data in a specialty repository, are all critical steps that necessarily will help investigators identify the key compounds, dosing paradigms and therapeutic windows to more successfully advance innovative therapies from the bench to the bedside. Both PRECISE-TBI and ODC-TBI are valuable community platforms for leading translational neurotrauma research into the next era.

References

- Agarwal, A., & Zhang, M. (2025). NeuroVR: A neurofeedback-based wearable headset enhanced by machine learning for treating neuro-AIDS. In *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5237226>
- Andersen, C.R., Wolf, J.T., Jennings, K., Prough, D.S., Hawkins, B.E. (2020). Moody Project Survival Analysis Morris Water Maze Dataset [Dataset]. In *Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury*. <https://doi.org/10.34945/F51591>
- Bandrowski, A., Brush, M., Grethe, J. S., Haendel, M. A., Kennedy, D. N., Hill, S., Hof, P. R., Martone, M. E., Pols, M., Tan, S., Washington, N., Zudilova-Seinstra, E., Vasilevsky, N., (2015). The Resource Identification Initiative: A cultural shift in publishing. *F1000Research*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.6555.2>
- Bandrowski, A., Grethe, J. S., Pilko, A., Gillespie, T., Pine, G., Patel, B., Surlles-Zeigler, M., & Martone, M. E. (2021). SPARC Data Structure: Rationale and Design of a FAIR Standard for Biomedical Research Data. In *bioRxiv* (p. 2021.02.10.430563). <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.02.10.430563>
- Bilder, G., Lin, J., & Neylon, C. (2015). Principles for open scholarly infrastructures. *Science in the Open*. <https://cameronneylon.net/blog/principles-for-open-scholarly-infrastructures/>
- Borghì, J. A., & Van Gulick, A. E. (2018). Data management and sharing in neuroimaging: Practices and perceptions of MRI researchers. *PloS One*, 13(7), e0200562.
- Buccilli, B. (2025). Associations between injury severity, fracture location, and ptsd risk in traumatic brain injury: Insights from the track-tbi pilot dataset. In *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5294875>
- Chou, A., Torres-Espín, A., Huie, J. R., Krukowski, K., Lee, S., Nolan, A., Guglielmetti, C., Hawkins, B. E., Chaumeil, M. M., Manley, G. T., Beattie, M. S., Bresnahan, J. C., Martone, M. E., Grethe, J. S., Rosi, S., & Ferguson, A. R. (2022). Empowering data sharing and analytics through the Open Data Commons for traumatic brain injury research. *Neurotrauma Reports*, 3(1), 139–157.
- Chow, M., & Ng, O. (2025). From technology adopters to creators: Leveraging AI-assisted vibe coding to transform clinical teaching and learning. *Medical Teacher*, 1–3.
- Clark, T., Caufield, H., Parker, J. A., Al Manir, S., Amorim, E., Eddy, J., Gim, N., Gow, B., Goar, W., Haendel, M., Hansen, J. N., Harris, N., Hermjakob, H., Joachimiak, M., Jordan, G., Lee, I.-H., McWeeney, S., Nebeker, C., Nikolov, M., ... Munoz-Torres, M. C. (2024). AI-readiness for biomedical data: Bridge2AI recommendations. In *bioRxiv.org*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.10.23.619844>
- Cousijn, H., Kenall, A., Ganley, E., Harrison, M., Kernohan, D., Lemberger, T., Murphy, F., Polischuk, P., Taylor, S., Martone, M., & Clark, T. (2018). A Data Citation Roadmap for Scientific Publishers. In *bioRxiv* (p. 100784). <https://doi.org/10.1101/100784>
- DANDI Archive*. (n.d.). Retrieved May 19, 2022, from <https://dandiarchive.org/dandiset/000148>
- Elshawi, R., Sakr, S., Talia, D., & Trunfio, P. (2018). Big data systems meet machine learning challenges: Towards big data science as a service. *Big Data Research*, 14, 1–11.
- Fenner, M., Crosas, M., Grethe, J. S., Kennedy, D., Hermjakob, H., Rocca-Serra, P., Durand, G., Berjon, R., Karcher, S., Martone, M., & Clark, T. (2019). A data citation roadmap for scholarly data repositories. *Scientific Data*, 6(1), 28.
- Ferguson, A. R., Nielson, J. L., Cragin, M. H., Bandrowski, A. E., & Martone, M. E. (2014). Big data from small data: data-sharing in the “long tail” of neuroscience. *Nature Neuroscience*, 17(11), 1442–1447.
- Fouad, K., Vavrek, R., Surlles-Zeigler, M. C., Huie, J. R., Radabaugh, H., Gurkoff, G. G., Visser, U., Grethe, J. S., Martone, M. E., Ferguson, A. R., Gensel, J. C., & Torres-Espin, A. (2023).

- A practical guide to data management and sharing for biomedical laboratory researchers. In *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8206341>
- Grethe, J. S., Bandrowski, A., Banks, D. E., Condit, C., Gupta, A., Larson, S. D., Li, Y., Ozyurt, I. B., Stagg, A. M., Whetzel, P.L., Marenco, L., Miller, P., Wang, R., Shepherd, G.M., Martone, M. E. (2014). SciCrunch: A cooperative and collaborative data and resource discovery platform for scientific communities. *Frontiers Events*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/conf.fninf.2014.18.00069>
- Hawkins, B. E., Huie, J. R., Almeida, C., Chen, J., & Ferguson, A. R. (2020). Data dissemination: Shortening the long tail of traumatic brain injury dark data. *Journal of Neurotrauma*, 37(22), 2414–2423.
- Huie, J. R., Nielson, J. L., Wolfsbane, J., Andersen, C. R., Spratt, H. M., DeWitt, D. S., Ferguson, A. R., & Hawkins, B. E. (2022). Data-driven approach to integrating genomic and behavioral preclinical traumatic brain injury research. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 10, 887898.
- Iorio, E. G., Khanteymooori, A., Fond, K. A., Keller, A. V., Davis, L. M., Schwab, J. M., Ferguson, A. R., Torres-Espin, A., & Watzlawick, R. (2024). Effect-Size Discrepancies in Literature Versus Raw Datasets from Experimental Spinal Cord Injury Studies: A CLIMBER Meta-Analysis. *Neurotrauma Reports*, 5(1), 686–698.
- Kislik, G., Fox, R., Korotcov, A., Zhou, J., Febo, M., Moghadas, B., Bibic, A., Zou, Y., Wan, J., Koehler, R., Adebayo, T., Burns, M., McCabe, J., Wang, K., Russell Huie, J., Ferguson, A., Paydar, A., Wanner, I., & Harris, N. (2025). *Harmonization of Multi-Site DTI Data from Left Hemisphere Sprague-Dawley Male and Female Rat CCI Injury: A Translational Outcomes Project in NeuroTrauma (TOP-NT) Consortium Study* [Dataset]. <http://doi.org/10.34945/F5D60C>
- Koloski, M., & Ramanathan, D. (2025). *Chronic Behavior on a self-paced probabilistic reversal learning task in male Long-Evans rats with severe, frontal bilateral controlled cortical impact* [Dataset]. <http://doi.org/10.34945/F50W3P>
- Kratz, J. E., & Strasser, C. (2015). Comment: Making data count. *Scientific Data*, 2, 150039.
- Kush, R. D., Warzel, D., Kush, M. A., Sherman, A., Navarro, E. A., Fitzmartin, R., Pétavy, F., Galvez, J., Becnel, L. B., Zhou, F. L., Harmon, N., Jauregui, B., Jackson, T., & Hudson, L. (2020). FAIR data sharing: The roles of common data elements and harmonization. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 107(103421), 103421.
- LaPlaca, M. C., Huie, J. R., Alam, H. B., Bachstetter, A. D., Bayir, H., Bellgowan, P. F., Cummings, D., Dixon, C. E., Ferguson, A. R., Ferland-Beckham, C., Floyd, C. L., Friess, S. H., Galanopoulou, A. S., Hall, E. D., Harris, N. G., Hawkins, B. E., Hicks, R. R., Hulbert, L. E., Johnson, V. E., ... Zai, L. J. (2021). Pre-clinical common data elements for traumatic brain injury research: Progress and use cases. *Journal of Neurotrauma*, 38(10), 1399–1410.
- Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., De Giusti, M., L'Hours, H., Hugo, W., Jenkyns, R., Khodiyar, V., Martone, M. E., Mokrane, M., Navale, V., Petters, J., Sierman, B., Sokolova, D. V., Stockhouse, M., & Westbrook, J. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), 144.
- Lowenberg, D. (2021). *Data Citation: Prioritizing Adoption*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4726087>
- Martone, M. (2023, November 13). *Incentivizing data-sharing in neuroscience: How about a little customer service?* The Transmitter: Neuroscience News and Perspectives. <https://www.thetransmitter.org/open-neuroscience-and-data-sharing/incentivizing-data-sharing-in-neuroscience-how-about-a-little-customer-service/>
- Martone, M. (2025). *Analysis of descriptive metadata of public data in the Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury (ODC-TBI) as of June 2025* [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17945371>

- Martone, M. E. (2023). The past, present and future of neuroscience data sharing: a perspective on the state of practices and infrastructure for FAIR. *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*, *17*, 1276407.
- Martone, M., & Nakamura, R. (2022). Changing the culture on data management and sharing: Getting ready for the new NIH data sharing policy. *Harvard Data Science Review*, *4*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.6650ce2b>
- Moore, J. H., & Tatonetti, N. (2025). Vibe coding: a new paradigm for biomedical software development. *BioData Mining*, *18*(1), 46.
- Murphy, F., Bar-Sinai, M., & Martone, M. E. (2021). A tool for assessing alignment of biomedical data repositories with open, FAIR, citation and trustworthy principles. *PloS One*, *16*(7), e0253538.
- Nielson, J., Cooper, S., Yue, J., Sorani, M., Inoue, T., Yuh, E., Lum, P., Carlsson, G., Vassar, M., Lingsma, H., Gordon, W., Valadka, A., Okonkwo, D., Manley, G., & Ferguson, A. (2023). *Imaging Features, Functional Recovery, and Selected Single Nucleotide Polymorphism Data from TRACK-TBI Pilot Dataset* [Dataset]. <http://doi.org/10.34945/F5RW24>
- NIH Funding Announcements to Align with NIH Initiative to Prioritize Human-based Research. (n.d.). Retrieved October 22, 2025, from <https://grants.nih.gov/news-events/nih-extramural-nexus-news/2025/07/nih-funding-announcements-to-align-with-nih-initiative-to-prioritize-human-based-research>
- NIH to prioritize human-based research technologies. (n.d.). National Institutes of Health (NIH). Retrieved August 8, 2025, from <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/nih-prioritize-human-based-research-technologies>
- Norris, C., Murphy, S., VandeVord, P., & Weatherbee, J. (2024). *Quantifying acute changes in neurometabolism following blast-induced traumatic brain injury in male Sprague Dawley rats* [Dataset]. <http://doi.org/10.34945/F5BP43>
- NOT-OD-21-013: Final NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing. (n.d.). Retrieved November 21, 2021, from <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-21-013.html>
- Osanlouy, M., Bandrowski, A., de Bono, B., Brooks, D., Cassarà, A. M., Christie, R., Ebrahimi, N., Gillespie, T., Grethe, J. S., Guercio, L. A., Heal, M., Lin, M., Kuster, N., Martone, M. E., Neufeld, E., Nickerson, D. P., Soltani, E. G., Tappan, S., Wagenaar, J. B., ... Hunter, P. J. (2021). The SPARC DRC: Building a Resource for the Autonomic Nervous System Community. *Frontiers in Physiology*, *12*, 693735.
- Poldrack, R. A., Markiewicz, C. J., Appelhoff, S., Ashar, Y. K., Auer, T., Baillet, S., Bansal, S., Beltrachini, L., Benar, C. G., Bertazzoli, G., Bhogawar, S., Blair, R. W., Bortoletto, M., Boudreau, M., Brooks, T. L., Calhoun, V. D., Castelli, F. M., Clement, P., Cohen, A. L., ... Gorgolewski, K. J. (2023). The Past, Present, and Future of the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS). In *arXiv [q-bio.OT]*. arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2309.05768>
- Radabaugh, H. L., Ferguson, A. R., Bramlett, H. M., & Dietrich, W. D. (2023). Increasing Rigor of Preclinical Research to Maximize Opportunities for Translation. *Neurotherapeutics: The Journal of the American Society for Experimental Neurotherapeutics*, *20*(6), 1433–1445.
- Radabaugh, H. L., Harris, N. G., Wanner, I. B., Burns, M. P., McCabe, J. T., Korotcov, A. V., Dardzinski, B. J., Zhou, J., Koehler, R. C., Wan, J., Allende Labastida, J., Moghadas, B., Bibic, A., Febo, M., Kobeissy, F. H., Zhu, J., Rubenstein, R., Hou, J., Bose, P. K., ... TOP-NT Investigators. (2025). Translational Outcomes Project in Neurotrauma (TOP-NT) pre-clinical consortium study: A synopsis. *Journal of Neurotrauma*, *42*(9-10), 898–912.
- Selecting a Data Repository. (n.d.). Retrieved September 30, 2025, from <https://grants.nih.gov/policy-and-compliance/policy-topics/sharing-policies/dms/selecting-a-data-repository>
- Starr, J., Castro, E., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Downs, R. R., Duerr, R., Haak, L. L., Haendel,

- M., Herman, I., Hodson, S., Hourclé, J., Kratz, J. E., Lin, J., Nielsen, L. H., Nurnberger, A., Proell, S., Rauber, A., Sacchi, S., Smith, A., ... Clark, T. (2015). Achieving human and machine accessibility of cited data in scholarly publications. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 1, e1.
- Subash, P., Gray, A., Boswell, M., Cohen, S. L., Garner, R., Salehi, S., Fisher, C., Hobel, S., Ghosh, S., Halchenko, Y., Dichter, B., Poldrack, R. A., Markiewicz, C., Hermes, D., Delorme, A., Makeig, S., Behan, B., Sparks, A., Arnott, S. R., ... Duncan, D. (2023a). A Comparison of Neuroelectrophysiology Databases. *ArXiv*.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/37426452>
- Subash, P., Gray, A., Boswell, M., Cohen, S. L., Garner, R., Salehi, S., Fisher, C., Hobel, S., Ghosh, S., Halchenko, Y., Dichter, B., Poldrack, R. A., Markiewicz, C., Hermes, D., Delorme, A., Makeig, S., Behan, B., Sparks, A., Arnott, S. R., ... Duncan, D. (2023b). A comparison of neuroelectrophysiology databases. *Scientific Data*, 10(1), 719.
- Surles-Zeigler, M. C., Sincomb, T., Gillespie, T. H., de Bono, B., Bresnahan, J., Mawe, G. M., Grethe, J. S., Tappan, S., Heal, M., & Martone, M. E. (2021). Extending and using anatomical vocabularies in the Stimulating Peripheral Activity to Relieve Conditions (SPARC) project. In *bioRxiv* (p. 2021.11.15.467961).
<https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.11.15.467961>
- Torres-Espín, A., Haefeli, J., Ehsanian, R., Torres, D., Almeida, C. A., Huie, J. R., Chou, A., Morozov, D., Sanderson, N., Dirlikov, B., Suen, C. G., Nielson, J. L., Kyritsis, N., Hemmerle, D. D., Talbott, J. F., Manley, G. T., Dhall, S. S., Whetstone, W. D., Bresnahan, J. C., ... TRACK-SCI Investigators. (2021). Topological network analysis of patient similarity for precision management of acute blood pressure in spinal cord injury. *eLife*, 10.
<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.68015>
- Wanner, I.-B., McCabe, J. T., Huie, J. R., Harris, N. G., Paydar, A., McMann-Chapman, C., Tobar, A., Korotcov, A., Burns, M. P., Koehler, R. C., Wan, J., Allende Labastida, J., Tong, J., Zhou, J., Davis, L. M., Radabaugh, H. L., Ferguson, A. R., Van Meter, T. E., Febo, M., ... TOP-NT Consortium Investigators. (2025). Prospective harmonization, common data elements, and sharing strategies for multicenter pre-clinical traumatic brain injury research in the Translational Outcomes Project in NeuroTrauma consortium. *Journal of Neurotrauma*, 42(9-10), 877–897.
- Whetzel, P. L., Grethe, J. S., Banks, D. E., & Martone, M. E. (2015). The NIDDK Information Network: A Community Portal for Finding Data, Materials, and Tools for Researchers Studying Diabetes, Digestive, and Kidney Diseases. *PLoS One*, 10(9), e0136206.
- Wickham, H. (2014). Tidy Data. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 59(10).
<https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v059.i10>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Musen, M. A. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018.